

MANAGEMENT OF CLASSROOM: ATTITUDE OF GOVERNMENT AND PRIVATE SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS

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ABSTRACT:

Classroom management is an important component of the teaching-learning process that helps teachers create an organized, disciplined, and supportive learning environment. The present study aims to examine the attitude of secondary school teachers towards classroom management with respect to gender and type of school. It focuses on comparing the mean scores of male and female teachers, government and private school teachers, and different combinations of these groups. The study follows a quantitative and qualitative approach that adopts a descriptive survey research design. Data were collected using a self-constructed attitude scale developed by the researchers. The reliability of the tool was established using the Spearman-Brown Coefficient. The collected data were analysed using appropriate statistical techniques, such as mean, standard deviation, degree of freedom, standard error of difference, and t-test, to determine the significance of differences among different groups of secondary school teachers. The study provides insights into teachers' attitudes towards classroom management and the influence of gender and type of school on their classroom management aspects. The findings of the study may be useful for teachers, school administrators, teacher educators, and policymakers in developing effective classroom management strategies and planning professional development programmes. The study also contributes to creating a positive atmosphere in secondary schools teacher mind.

KEYWORDS:

CLASSROOM MANAGEMENT, TEACHER ATTITUDE, SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS, GOVERNMENT SCHOOLS, PRIVATE SCHOOLS.

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1.0 INTRODUCTION

Education is a purposeful process that contributes to the intellectual, social, emotional, and moral development of individuals. The effectiveness of the teaching-learning process depends not only on curriculum and instructional methods but also on the environment in which learning takes place. A positive classroom environment encourages students' participation, motivation, and achievement. Therefore, classroom management becomes an essential element for creating an effective and supportive learning environment (Fraser, 2012). Classroom management refers to the systematic process through which teachers organize classroom activities, establish rules and procedures, manage students' behaviour, and maintain a favourable environment for learning. It includes various dimensions such as classroom discipline, teacher-student relationships, organization of learning activities, and effective use of instructional time. Evertson and Weinstein (2006), stated that classroom management involves

teacher actions aimed at creating an environment that supports academic learning as well as students' social and emotional development.

The attitude of teachers towards classroom management plays a significant role in determining the quality of classroom practices. Teachers with positive attitudes are more likely to adopt effective management strategies, maintain constructive relationships with students, and create a classroom atmosphere that promotes learning. According to Marzano, Marzano, and Pickering (2003), effective classroom management depends on teachers' ability to establish clear expectations, maintain appropriate behaviour, and develop positive classroom relationships. Teachers' attitudes towards classroom management may differ due to various personal and institutional factors. Gender is considered an important factor that may influence teachers' perceptions, communication styles, and approaches towards managing

classroom situations. Male and female teachers may differ in their classroom management approaches due to variations in experiences, beliefs, and teaching practices. Similarly, the type of school, such as government or private school, may influence teachers' classroom management attitudes because of differences in school resources, administrative support, workload, and organizational environment (Emmer & Sabornie, 2015).

The secondary school stage is an important phase of education where students background significant academic and developmental changes. At this level, teachers need effective classroom management skills to maintain discipline, encourage active participation, and create a positive learning environment. Effective classroom management not only improves classroom functioning but also contributes to students' academic and social development (Woolfolk, 2019).

2.0 SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

Classroom management is an important component of effective teaching and learning. A well-managed classroom provides a positive, disciplined, and supportive environment that helps students participate actively in the learning process. Teachers' attitudes towards classroom management influence their ability to organize classroom activities, maintain discipline, develop positive teacher-student relationships, and create favourable conditions for learning. The present study found the attitude of government and private secondary school teachers towards classroom management. It provides an understanding of the overall classroom management attitudes of secondary school teachers and highlights the differences based on gender and type of school. The comparison between male and female teachers, government and private school teachers, and different combinations of these groups may help identify variations in classroom management approaches.

The study will be beneficial for secondary school teachers by providing awareness about effective classroom management practices and encouraging them to develop positive attitudes towards classroom organization, student behaviour management, and classroom interaction. It may help teachers reflect on their own classroom practices and improve their professional effectiveness. The findings of the study may be useful for school administrators in understanding the factors influencing teachers' classroom management attitudes. It may assist them in providing appropriate support, resources, and professional development opportunities to enhance teachers' classroom management skills. The study may also be valuable for teacher educators and training institutions in designing need-based teacher education programmes. The findings may help in developing training modules focusing on classroom discipline, student engagement, classroom organization, and effective teaching strategies. The study also provides useful information for educational policymakers in developing policies and programmes aimed at improving the quality of secondary education. Finally, this study contributes to educational research by

providing information about teachers' attitudes towards classroom management. It can also help future researchers who want to study classroom management with different factors and in different educational settings.

3.0 OBJECTIVES

- a) To find out the mean scores of male and female secondary school teachers towards classroom management on the whole.
- b) To find out the mean scores of governments and private secondary school teachers towards classroom management.
- c) To find out the mean scores of government male secondary school teachers and government female secondary school teachers towards classroom management.
- d) To find out the mean scores of private male secondary school teachers and private female secondary school teachers towards classroom management.
- e) To find out the mean scores of Government male secondary school teachers and private male secondary school teachers towards classroom management.
- f) To find out the mean scores of Government female secondary school teachers and private female secondary school teachers towards classroom management.
- g) To find out the mean scores of government male secondary school teachers and private female secondary school teachers towards classroom management.
- h) To find out the mean scores of Government female secondary school teachers and private male secondary school teachers towards classroom management.

4.0 HYPOTHESES

- a) **H1:** There is no significant difference in the mean scores of male and female secondary school teachers towards classroom management on the whole.
- b) **H2:** There is no significant difference in the mean scores of government and private secondary school teachers towards classroom management.
- c) **H3:** There is no significant difference in the mean scores of government male secondary school teachers and government female secondary school teachers towards classroom management.
- d) **H4:** There is no significant difference in the mean scores of private male secondary school teachers and private female secondary school teachers towards classroom management.
- e) **H5:** There is no significant difference in the mean scores of Government male secondary school teachers and private male secondary school teachers towards classroom management.

- f) **H6:** There is no significant difference in the mean scores of Government female secondary school teachers and private female secondary school teachers towards classroom management.
- g) **H7:** There is no significant difference in the mean scores of government male secondary school teachers and private female secondary school teachers towards classroom management.
- h) **H8:** There is no significant difference in the mean scores of Government female secondary school teachers and private male secondary school teachers towards classroom management.

5.0 REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Pianta et al. (2002), studied the quality of pre-kindergarten programmes, classrooms, and teacher-child interactions across 238 classrooms from 6 states. The study found that classroom quality was lower for children living below the poverty line, mainly due to a lack of formal teacher training in early childhood education. The findings suggested that teacher quality plays a significant role in maintaining effective learning environments.

Rytivaara (2012), investigated classroom management in co-taught lessons through observations and interviews with primary school teachers. The study found that collaboration between teachers provides emotional support and allows flexible use of different roles, which positively influences classroom management.

Haloi (2022), studied students’ attitudes towards the availability of teaching-learning materials (TLM) in provincialized and private secondary schools of Kamrup District. The study adopted a descriptive survey method and collected data from 260 students using a self-structured questionnaire. The study found that private schools had better TLM facilities and suggested regular teacher orientation programmes for effective use of TLM.

Sharma (2018), examined teachers’ attitudes towards classroom management and found that teachers’ perceptions significantly influence student engagement and classroom discipline. The study emphasized the importance of continuous professional development programmes for enhancing teachers’ classroom management skills and effectiveness.

6.0 METHODOLOGY

a) Research Design

The present study is qualitative and quantitative in nature and adopts a descriptive survey research design. This design helps in collecting and analysing data to study the attitude of secondary school teachers towards classroom management in Kamrup district. For the purpose of data collection, a self-constructed attitude scale was developed and used by the researchers. The tool consists of a set of statements related to teachers’ attitudes towards classroom management skills, and teachers respond to these statements according to their level of agreement.

After collecting the data, the researchers analysed it using appropriate statistical techniques to identify differences in teachers’ attitudes. Therefore, the descriptive survey research design was selected by the researchers.

b) Population

In this study the researchers selected Kamrup district secondary school teachers in Assam State School Education Board (ASSEB), where the total number of schools is 845 and the number of teachers is 16464 (According to Unified Digital Information on School Education (UDISE) 2023-2024).

TABLE-1: POPULATION OF SCHOOL AND TEACHER IN KAMRUP DISTRICT

Type of schools	Total Number of School	Total number of Teacher
Government School	455	7727
Private School	390	8737
Total	845	16464

Source- Unified Digital Information on School Education (UDISE) 2023-2024, Assam

c) Sample

In this study, the researchers selected a sample of 1,621 participants from the total population of 16,464, representing 9.8% of the total population.

TABLE-2: SAMPLE OF SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHER IN KAMRUP RURAL AND URBAN(M)

Gender	Type of school		Total
	Government Teachers	Private Teachers	
Male	307	297	604
Female	573	444	1017
Total	880	741	1621

d) Tools

The tool was developed by the researchers with the support of experts. The developed tool was administered through a pilot study, and its reliability was established using the Spearman-Brown Coefficient. The reliability value of the tool was found to be 0.76. The attitude scale consists of 56 statements, including 27 positive statements and 29 negative statements.

e) Procedure Of Data Collection

The data for the present study were collected through a self-constructed attitude scale. For the purpose of data collection, the researchers personally visited the selected secondary schools and distributed the attitude scale among the teachers. The researchers provided necessary instructions regarding the completion of the attitude scale. After completion of the data collection the researcher carefully checked, organized, and prepared for further analysis using appropriate statistical techniques like standard deviation, mean, t-test etc.

f) Statistical Techniques

For the analysis and interpretation of the collected data, the researcher used appropriate statistical techniques like

Mean, Standard Deviation, t-test etc which were calculated to determine the average scores and variability of teachers' attitudes towards classroom management. The Degree of Freedom (DF), Standard Error of Difference (SED), and *t*-value were calculated to examine the significance of differences between the groups.

7.0 DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATIONS

Objectives1: To find out the mean scores of male and female secondary school teachers towards classroom management on the whole.

H1 There is no significant difference in the mean scores of male and female secondary school teachers towards classroom management on the whole.

TABLE-3: MEAN SCORES OF DIFFERENCES BETWEEN MALE AND FEMALE SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS' ATTITUDE TOWARDS CLASSROOM MANAGEMENT ON THE WHOLE

Category	N	M	SD	DF	SED	t value	Level of significance at 0.01 level
Male	604	172.78	3.58	1619	0.17	0.12	Not significant
Female	1017	172.80	3.48				

df=1619 at 0.05=1.96; 0.01=2.58

For the mean difference between male and female secondary school teacher attitude towards classroom management from the table-3 the calculated *t* value is found to be 0.12 which is not significant at 0.01 level of significance when the df is 1619. Therefore, the constructed hypothesis, "There is no significant difference in the mean scores of male and female secondary school teachers towards classroom management on the whole" is retained, which means not rejected. But the mean value of the female secondary school teachers (172.80) and male secondary school teachers (172.78) indicates female secondary school teachers possess slightly better attitude than male secondary school teachers in classroom management.

Objectives 2 To find out the mean scores of government and private secondary school teachers towards classroom management.

H2: There is no significant difference in the mean scores of government and private secondary school teachers towards classroom management.

TABLE-4: MEAN SCORES OF DIFFERENCE BETWEEN GOVERNMENT AND PRIVATE SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS TOWARDS CLASSROOM MANAGEMENT

Category	N	M	SD	DF	SED	t value	Level of significance at 0.01 level
Government	880	173.11	3.50	1619	0.17	4.12	significant
Private	741	172.41	3.49				

df=1619 at 0.05=1.96; 0.01=2.58

For the mean difference between government and private secondary school teacher attitude towards classroom management from the table-4 the calculated *t*-value is found to be 4.12 which is significant at 0.01 level of significance when the df is 1619. Therefore, the constructed hypothesis, "There is no significant difference in the mean scores of governments and private secondary school teachers towards classroom management" is not retained, which means not accepted. But the mean value of the government secondary school teachers (173.11) and private secondary school teachers (172.41) indicates government secondary school teachers possess slightly better attitude than private secondary school teachers in classroom management.

Objectives 3: To find out the mean scores of government male secondary school teachers and government female secondary school teachers towards classroom management.

H3 There is no significant difference in the mean scores of government male secondary school teachers and government female secondary school teachers towards classroom management.

TABLE-5: MEAN SCORES OF DIFFERENCE BETWEEN GOVERNMENT MALE SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS AND GOVERNMENT FEMALE SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS TOWARDS CLASSROOM MANAGEMENT

Category	N	M	SD	DF	SED	t value	Level of significance 0.01 level
Govt. Male	307	173.10	3.53	878	0.24	0.04	Not significant
Govt. Female	573	173.11	3.49				

df=878 at 0.05=1.96; 0.01=2.58

For the mean difference between government male and government female secondary school teacher attitude towards classroom management from the table-5 the calculated *t* value is found to be 0.04 which is not significant at 0.01 level of significance. When the df is 878. Therefore, the constructed hypothesis, "There is no significant difference in the mean scores of government male secondary school teachers and government female secondary school teachers towards classroom management." is retained, which means not rejected. But the mean value of the government male secondary school teachers (173.10) and government female secondary school teachers (173.11) indicates government female secondary school teachers possess slightly better attitude than government male secondary school teachers in classroom management.

Objectives 4: To find out the mean scores of private male secondary school teachers and private female secondary school teachers towards classroom management.

H4: There is no significant difference in the mean scores of private male secondary school teachers and private female secondary school teachers towards classroom

management.

TABLE-6: MEAN SCORES OF DIFFERENCE BETWEEN PRIVATE MALE SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS AND PRIVATE FEMALE SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS TOWARDS CLASSROOM MANAGEMENT

Category	N	M	SD	DF	SED	t value	Level of significance 0.01 level
Private Male	297	172.45	3.60	739	0.26	0.23	Not significant
Private Female	444	172.39	3.42				

df=739 at 0.05=1.96; 0.01=2.58

For the mean difference between private male and private female secondary school teacher attitude towards classroom management from the table-6 the calculated t-value is found to be 0.23 which is not significant at 0.01 level of significance when the df is 739. Therefore, the constructed hypothesis, "There is no significant difference in the mean scores of private male secondary school teachers and private female secondary school teachers towards classroom management." is retained, which means not rejected. But, the mean value of the private male secondary school teachers (172.45) and private female secondary school teachers (172.39) indicates private male secondary school teachers possess slightly better attitude than private female secondary school teachers in classroom management.

Objectives 5: To find out the mean scores of Government male secondary school teachers and private male secondary school teachers towards classroom management.

H5 There is no significant difference in the mean scores of Government male secondary school teachers and private male secondary school teachers towards classroom management.

TABLE-7: MEAN SCORES OF DIFFERENCE BETWEEN GOVERNMENT MALE SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS AND PRIVATE MALE SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS TOWARDS CLASSROOM MANAGEMENT

Category	N	M	SD	DF	SED	t value	Level of significance 0.01 level
Govt. Male	307	173.10	3.53	739	0.28	2.32	Not significant
Private Male	297	172.45	3.60				

df=602 at 0.05=1.96; 0.01=2.58

For the mean difference between male and female secondary school teacher attitude towards classroom management from the table-7 the calculated t-value is found to be 2.32 which is significant at 0.01 level of significance. Therefore, the constructed hypothesis, "There is no significant difference in the mean scores of

government male secondary school teachers and private male secondary school teachers towards classroom management", is not retained, which means not accepted. But, the mean value of the government male secondary school teachers (173.10) and private male secondary school teachers (172.45) indicates government male secondary school teachers possess slightly better attitude than private male secondary school teachers in classroom management.

Objectives 6: To find out the mean scores of Government female secondary school teachers and private female secondary school teachers towards classroom management.

H6 There is no significant difference in the mean scores of Government female secondary school teachers and private female secondary school teachers towards classroom management.

TABLE-8: MEAN SCORES OF DIFFERENCE BETWEEN GOVERNMENT FEMALE SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS AND PRIVATE FEMALE SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS TOWARDS CLASSROOM MANAGEMENT

Category	N	M	SD	DF	SED	t value	Level of significance 0.01 level
Govt. Female	573	173.11	3.49	1015	0.22	3.27	significant
Private Female	444	172.39	3.41				

df=1015 at 0.05=1.96; 0.01=2.58

For the mean difference between Government female secondary school teachers and private female secondary school teacher's attitude towards classroom management from the table-8 the calculated t value is found to be 3.27 which is significant at 0.01 level of significance. Therefore, the constructed hypothesis, "There is no significant difference in the mean scores of Government female secondary school teachers and private female secondary school teachers towards classroom management." is not retained, which means not accepted. But the mean value of the government female secondary school teachers (173.11) and private female secondary school teachers (172.39) indicates government female secondary school teachers possess slightly better attitude than private female secondary school teachers in classroom management.

Objectives 7: To find out the mean scores of government male secondary school teachers and private female secondary school teachers towards classroom management.

H7: There is no significant difference in the mean scores of government male secondary school teachers and private female secondary school teachers towards classroom management.

TABLE-9: MEAN SCORES OF DIFFERENCE BETWEEN GOVERNMENT MALE SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS AND PRIVATE FEMALE SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS TOWARDS CLASSROOM MANAGEMENT

Category	N	M	SD	DF	SED	t value	Level of significance 0.01 level
Govt. Male	307	173.10	3.53	749	0.26	2.73	significant
Private Female	444	172.39	3.42				

df=749 at 0.05=1.96; 0.01=2.58

For the mean difference between government male secondary school teachers and private female secondary school teacher’s attitude towards classroom management from the table-9 the calculated t-value is found to be 2.73 which is significant at 0.01 level of significance. Therefore, the constructed hypothesis, “There is no significant difference in the mean scores of government male secondary school teachers and private female secondary school teachers towards classroom management,” is not retained, which means not accepted. But the mean value of the government male secondary school teachers (173.10) and private female secondary school teachers (172.39) indicates government male secondary school teachers possess slightly better attitude than private female secondary school teachers in classroom management.

Objectives 8: To find out the mean scores of Government female secondary school teachers and private male secondary school teachers towards classroom management.

H8: There is no significant difference in the mean scores of Government female secondary school teachers and private male secondary school teachers towards classroom management.

TABLE-10: MEAN SCORES OF DIFFERENCE BETWEEN GOVERNMENT FEMALE SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS AND PRIVATE MALE SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS TOWARDS CLASSROOM MANAGEMENT

Category	N	M	SD	DF	SED	t value	Level of significance 0.01 level
Govt. Female	573	173.11	3.49	868	0.24	2.75	significant
Private Male	444	172.45	3.60				

df=868at 0.05=1.96; 0.01=2.58

For the mean difference between government female secondary school teachers and private male secondary school teacher’s attitude towards classroom management from the table-10 the calculated t-value is found to be 2.75 which is significant at 0.01 level of significance. Therefore, the constructed hypothesis, “There is no significant difference in the mean scores of government female

secondary school teachers and private male secondary school teachers towards classroom management.” is not retained, which means not accepted. But the mean value of the government female secondary school teachers (173.11) and private male secondary school teachers (172.45) indicates government female secondary school teachers possesses slightly better attitude than private male secondary school teachers in classroom management.

8.0 MAJOR FINDINGS

- a) Female secondary school teachers possess slightly better attitude than male secondary school teachers in classroom management.
- b) Government secondary school teachers possess slightly better attitude than private secondary school teachers in classroom management.
- c) Government female secondary school teachers possess slightly better attitude than government male secondary school teachers in classroom management.
- d) Private male secondary school teachers possess slightly better attitude than private female secondary school teachers in classroom management.
- e) Government male secondary school teachers possess slightly better attitude than private male secondary school teachers in classroom management.
- f) Government female secondary school teachers possess slightly better attitude than private female secondary school teachers in classroom management.
- g) Government male secondary school teachers possess slightly better attitude than private female secondary school teachers in classroom management.
- h) Government female secondary school teachers possess slightly better attitude than private male secondary school teachers in classroom management.

9.0 SUGGESTIONS

Based on the findings and conclusions of the present study, some suggestions have been provided to improve classroom management practices among secondary school teachers. These suggestions may help teachers, school administrators, and educational authorities in developing effective strategies for creating a positive and conducive learning environment.

- a) Regular training programmes, workshops, and seminars should be organized for secondary school teachers to enhance their classroom management skills. These programmes must focus on effective strategies for maintaining discipline, managing student behaviour, creating a positive learning environment, and improving teacher-student interaction.
- b) Teacher education institutions can give more emphasis to classroom management skills during pre-service and in-service teacher training programmes. Practical knowledge and classroom-based experiences can be included to

prepare teachers for handling different classroom situations.

- c) Teachers can adopt student-centred approaches and create a supportive classroom atmosphere where students feel motivated, respected, and actively involved in the learning process.
- d) School authorities can provide adequate support, resources, and guidance to teachers for effective classroom management. A cooperative environment between teachers, administrators, and students must be developed to improve classroom functioning.
- e) Educational authorities can focus on improving classroom management practices in both government and private schools by providing necessary resources, training opportunities, and professional support according to the needs of teachers.
- f) Teachers can be encouraged to share their classroom management experiences, innovative practices, and effective strategies through teacher networks, meetings, and collaborative activities.
- g) Future researchers may be conducted in similar studies by including other variables such as teaching experience, academic qualification, subject specialization, location of school, and school environment to gain deeper insights into classroom management practices.

10.0 CONCLUSION

Classroom management is a fundamental component of the teaching-learning process, as it directly influences the quality of classroom interaction, student engagement, and the overall learning environment. The present study entitled "Management of Classroom: Attitude of Government and Private Secondary School Teachers" was conducted to examine the attitude of secondary school teachers towards classroom management with respect to gender and type of school. The study aimed to find out the mean scores of male and female secondary school teachers, government and private secondary school teachers, and different combinations of these groups towards classroom management. The analysis of data through appropriate statistical techniques such as mean, standard deviation, degree of freedom, standard error of difference, and *t*-value helped the researchers to identify the differences in teachers' attitudes towards classroom management.

The findings of the study provide valuable insights into the perceptions and attitudes of secondary school teachers regarding classroom management. Classroom management is a multidimensional process that includes maintaining discipline, organizing classroom activities, creating a conducive learning environment, implementing effective instructional procedures, and using appropriate evaluation strategies. Teachers' positive attitudes towards these aspects contribute significantly to effective classroom functioning. The study highlights that teachers' attitudes towards classroom management are influenced

by various factors, including gender and institutional background. The comparison between government and private school teachers provides an understanding of how different school environments, available resources, administrative support, and working conditions may affect teachers' classroom management approaches. Similarly, the comparison between male and female teachers helps to understand the role of gender in shaping classroom management attitudes. Effective classroom management requires not only knowledge of teaching methods but also skills related to classroom organization, student behaviour management, communication, and maintaining positive relationships with learners. Teachers who possess positive attitudes towards classroom management are better able to create an environment that encourages student participation, motivation, and academic growth. The findings of the study may be beneficial for secondary school teachers by encouraging them to develop effective classroom management strategies and improve their professional practices. It may help teachers identify the importance of maintaining a supportive classroom atmosphere and adopting appropriate approaches according to students' needs. The study may also provide useful information to school administrators and educational authorities for planning professional development programmes, workshops, and training activities related to classroom management. Such initiatives can enhance teachers' competencies and help them deal effectively with classroom challenges. Overall, the study contributes to the existing body of educational research by providing empirical evidence regarding teachers' attitudes towards classroom management in secondary schools. It may serve as a reference for future researchers who intend to study classroom management in relation to other variables such as teaching experience, academic qualification, subject specialization, and school environment.

In conclusion, effective classroom management is essential for achieving meaningful learning outcomes and maintaining a positive educational environment. The attitude of teachers play a crucial role in determining the effectiveness of classroom management practices. Therefore, continuous professional development and support for teachers are necessary to strengthen classroom management skills and improve the quality of education in both government and private secondary schools.

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